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TEMPORAL MA'NOLI SO'ZLARNING INGLIZCHA O'ZBEKCHA TIPOLOGIYASI

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Annotasiya: Xorijiy tilni o'rganuvchilar o'rganayotgan tilning leksika va grammatikasini o'z ona tillariga taqqoslagan holda o'rganadilar. Shundan kelib chiqib maqolada vaqtni ifodalovchi birliklarning ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ishlatilish usullari haqida so'z boradi. Leksik materialning mazmuni, iboralar, predlogli birikmalar va so'z birikmalari hamda ularni o'zbek tilida mos variantlari asarlardan olingan misollar orqali tushuntirilgan.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: Adverbial elementlar, temporal sintagma, predloglar, leksik birliklar, payt ergash gap, bosh gap, ravish, fe'l, ot, predlogli birikmalar.

ENGLISH-UZBEK TYPOLOGY OF TIME EXPRESSING WORDS

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Abstract. Foreign language learners study the vocabulary and grammar of the target language by comparing it with their native language. Based on this, the article discusses the ways of using units of time in English and Uzbek languages. The content of lexical material, phraseological units, prepositional phrases, as well as their equivalents in the Uzbek language is explained using examples from the works of writers.

Key words: Adverbial elements, temporal syntagma, prepositions, lexical units, subordinate clause of time, main clause, adverb, verb, noun, prepositional phrases.

ANGLO-UZBEKSKAYA TIPOLOGIYA SLOV, OBOZNACHAYUSHIX VREMYA

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Annotasiya. Izuchayuvchiye inostrannyy yazyk izuchayut leksiku i grammatiku izuchayemogo yazyka, sravnivaya yego so svoim rodnyim yazykom. Isxodya iz etogo v statye rassmatrivayutsya sposoby upotrebleniya yedinis vremeni v angliyskom i uzbekskom yazykax. Soderjaniye leksicheskogo materiala, frazeologizmov, slovosochetaniy s predlogami, a takje ix sootvetstviyuyuchiye varianty v uzbekskom yazyke poyasnyayetsya na primerax iz proizvedeniy.

Klyuchevyye slova i slovosochetaniya: Adverbialnyye elementy, temporalnaya sintagma, predlogi, leksicheskiye yedinisy, pridatochnoye predlojeniye vremeni, glavnoye predlojeniye, narechiye, glagol, suuyestvitelnoye, slovosochetaniya s predlogami.

Kirish

Qaysi tilni o'rganmaylik, temporallikni ifodalovchi birliklarni o'rganmasdan ilojimiz yo'q. Chunki sodir etilayotgan har qanday voqea-hodisa vaqt va makonda amalga oshiriladi. Temporal ma'nolar ma'lum va aniq temporal birliklar bilan, til birliklari – ravishlar, fe'llar, otlar, sifatlar yordamida yuzaga keladi. Ingliz tilida payt holini turli sintaktik birliklar orqali ifodalash mumkin. A.M. Muxin payt holini ifodalovchi sintaktik birliklarning differensial sintaktik-semantik belgisini temporallik atamasi bilan ataydi. Shunga ko'ra ingliz va o'zbek tillarida temporallikni ifodalovchi sintaktik birliklar quyidagicha namoyon bo'ladi. Temporal sintegmasini ifodalovchi birliklar gap

qurilmasida kesimga bog'lanib, unda ifodalangan ish-harakatning tugallanganligini, davomiyligini, chegaralanganligini, nutq jarayonidan keyin bajarilishini va ish-harakatning bajarilishida ketma-ketlikni ifodalashi mumkin.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiyasi

Ushbu maqolamizda Temporallikni ifodalovchi adverbial elementlar, predloglar orqali va paytni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar yordamida ham ish-harakatning bajarilish paytini ifodalashi mumkin. Ularni maqolamizda ko'rib chiqamiz.

Adverbial (ravishli) yelementlar bilan ifodalangan temporal birliklar quyidagilar:

Oddiy ravishlar

yet	- hali, hanuz
never	- hech qachon
now	- hozir
still	- hamon
ever	- bir paytlar, biror payt
just	- hozirgina, faqat
already	- allaqachon
always	- har doim
sometimes	- ba'zan
often	- tez-tez, ko'pincha
then	- keyin, shu payt, o'shanda

- **Yet – hali** – bu kesimning inkor shaklida uchraydi: Jim had not yet seen his beautiful present . (OH, The gift of the Magi 5); Pardozhchilar hali-veri ishga tushmaydi, - dedim xotirjamlik bilan. (O'H, 5, Ikki eshik orasi)

- **Never – hech qachon**: Jim was never late. (OH, The gift of the Magi 3); U tong otishi-yu, kech kirishini hech qachon shunchalik orziqib kutmagandi. (uzun kechalar, O'H 61, Uzun kechalar)

- **Now – hozir**: So now Della's beautiful hair fell about her, rippling and shining like a cascade of brown waters. (OH, The gift of the Magi 2); hozir dilsiyohlik bo'lishini bilib, yuragim g'ash tortdi (O'H, 4, Ikki eshik orasi);

- **Still – hamon**: With a whirl of skirts and with the brilliant sparkle still in her eyes, she cluttered out of the door and down the stairs to the street (OH, The gift of the Magi 2);Tushim hamon ko'z oldimdan ketmas, dadamni yo'qotib qo'yganim alam qilardi (O'H, 53, Ikki eshik orasi);

- **Ever – bir paytlar, biror payt**: Maybe the hairs of my head were numbered," she went on with a sudden serious sweetness, "but nobody could ever count my love for you. Shall I put the chops on, Jim?" (OH, The gift of the Magi 4); Bir paytlar o'zining bolaligi o'tgan hovli o'rnida to'rt qavatli uy qurilibdi. Yong'oqzor qirqilib ketibdi.(O'H, 189, Bahor qaytmaydi);

- **Once – bir vaqtlar**: Robert Cohn was once Middleweight boxing champion of Prinstone (EH, A cosmopolite in a café, 11); Bir vaqtlar mana shu uyga yor-yor bilan kirib kelganini haligina orziqib eslamaganmidi!(O'H, Cho'l havosi 222);

- **Just – hozirgina, faqat**: "I'm not cold," she said. "I was just thinking. I ought to tell you something" (OH, Blind man`s holiday 22); Hilola bir nafas jim bordi-da, hozirgina ekranda ko'rgan voqealardan yana hayajonlanib ketdi. (O'H, Uzun kechalar, 67);

- **Already – allaqachon**: But whenever Mr. James Dillingham Young came home and reached his flat above he was called "Jim" and greatly hugged by Mrs. James Dillingham Young, already

introduced to you as Della. (OH, The gift of the Magi,1); Ammo Shodivoy *allaqachon* o'tliqning oldiga borib olgan, qo'shqo'llab so'rashar edi. Alimardon uning oxirgi gaplarini eshitib qoldi. (O'H, Cho'l havosi, 268);

- **Always – har doim:** Della doubled the fob chain in her hand and sat on the corner of the table near the door that he *always* entered. (OH, The gift of the Magi, 3); U *har doim* molini bizlarga qaytartirardi. Nimagadir bu safar o'jarligim tutdi. (O'H, Hurkitilgan qush, 30);

- **then o'zbek tiliga keyin, shu payt, o'shanda** kabilar yordamida tarjima qilinadi: Then she heard his step on the stair away down on the first flight, and she turned white for just a moment. (OH, The gift of the Magi, 3); *Keyin* qo'lidagi tol yog'och bilan imo qilib ko'rsatdi. – Dadasiga o'xshagan daroz ekan. (O'H, Hurkitilgan qush, 30); *Then* all of a sudden I started to cry (EH, 36); *Shu payt* ichkari uyning ham eshigi ochilib, ostonada onasi ko'rindi. (O'H, Qalbingga quloq sol, 357); *Then* you'd know these things (EH,108); O'shanda onasi unga guruch yuvilgan suvni ichirgani Muniraning esida qolgan. (O'H, Baxt, 35);

- **Sometimes – ba'zan:** Grand as the watch was, he *sometimes* looked at it on the sly on account of the old leather strap that he used in place of a chain.

(OH, The gift of the Magi,4); Kimsan akam men o'ylagandek yomon bola emas ekan. Ba'zan rahmim keladi unga (O'H, Ikki eshik orasi 46,);

- **During +ko'rsatish olmoshi yoki son +ot – bu paytda, ... mobaynida:**

During this time Robert's mother had settled an allowance on him about three hundred dollars a month (EH,13); *Bu paytda* Robertning onasi unga oyiga uch yuz dollardan pul yubora boshlagan edi. (EH,5); *During these three years*, the first spend in travel, the last two in Paris (EH,13); Mana shu *uch yil mobaynida* birinchi yilni sayohat bilan o'tkazishdi, keyingi yili Parijda bo'lishdi (EH,5);

Adverbial elementlardan tashqari, ingliz tilida turlicha predloglar bilan hafta kun nomlari, oylar, yillar, ovqatlanish paytini ifodalovchi leksik birliklar birikib kelib, temporallikni ifodalasa, o'zbek tilida temporallikni ifodalovchi otlar, sifatdoshlar, har xil kelishik qo'shimchalaridan foydalaniladi. "... predloglarning alohida so'z turkumi sifatida o'ziga xos xususiyatlari sintaktik darajada ko'zga tashlanadi. Ular sintaktik konstruksiya tarkibida alohida so'z sifatida aniq ajralib turadi va birikmaning markazi hamda tobelanuvchi komponentlari o'rtasida tobe aloqani ifodalash vazifasini bajaradi" [6;144]. Maqolamizning ushbu qismida temporallikni ifodalovchi predlogli birikmalarga e'tibor qaratamiz.

- After + ot – ot+dan+keyin: Klein proposes a stroll *after dinner*; and me and him and Silver walks down toward Seventh Avenue to see the sights. (OH, Babes in the jungle, 16); Munira sakkizinchi sinfni bitirganidan keyin Oloy bozori biqinidagi tikuvchilik atelyesiga ishga kirdi. (O'H, Baxt, 36);

- **Ot+before – bundan+son+oldin:** He had come in with me an hour before. (EH, 138); O'zidan *oldin* Anvarning ish boshlagani, quvonch bilan gapirishi unga yoqmad. (O'H, Bahor qaytmaydi,132);

- **Before – ilgari ham:** Before there was a royal family they called the man "Whispering Ben." (OH, The princess and the Puma, 40); Yo'q, eshitgandi, bir vaqtlar, kelin bo'lmasidan ilgari... (O'H, Bahor qaytmaydi, 226);

- **Before + son – son+dan+ilgari:** *Before the first year* had passed I had saved a thousand dollars, and we had lived in comfort. (OH Confessions of a Humorist, 50) Qamal bo'lmasidan *bir hafta ilgari* qiz yigitlardan biriga – o'z sevganiga tekkan ekan. (O'H, Bahor qaytmaydi,140)

- **At+ot – ot+sifatdosh+da:** Tell you some more *at lunch* (EH,110) Qolganini tushlik qilayotganimizda gapirib beraman. (EH, Bahor qaytmaydi, 196)

- **At+ son+ ot – ot+son+da:** *At three o'clock* Klein brought his Wall Street friend to see us in Silver's room. (OH, Babes in the Jungle,15); *Ertaga – 24 mart kuni soat 13 da* 3-kurs studentlarining umumiy komsomol yig'ilishi bo'ladi. (O'H, Qalbingga quloq sol, 458);

- **For+ son+ ot - son+ ot+davomida:** Tomorrow would be Christmas Day, and she had only \$1.87 with which to buy Jim a present. She had been saving every penny she could *for months*, with this result. (OH, The Gift of the Magi,1) *Shu kunlar davomida* Hilola bilan ham durustroq gaplashmaganini, qiz undan qachondir, negadir ranjib qolganini tush kabi g'ira-shira esladi. (O'H, Uzun kechalar,77)

Temporallikni ifodalovchi sintaktik birliklar nafaqat adverbial elementlar, paytni yoki vaqtni ifodalovchi sintaktik birliklar predloglar yordamida ifodalanadi, balki paytni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar yordamida ham ish-harakatning bajarilish paytini ifodalashi mumkin. Masalan: *tomorrow-ertaga, yesterday-kecha, Thursday-payshanba, tonight-bugun kechqurun*, hamda paytni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar bilan ayrim *ravish, son, olmosh* kabilar birikib kelishi yordamida ham ish-harakatning tugaganligini, davomiyligini, hali ro'yobga chiqmaganligi kabi zamon shakllarining ifodalanishiga aniqlik kiritadi.

- **One day – bir kuni:** I struck New York about noon *one day*, and took a walk up Broadway.(OH, Babes in the jungle, 12); *Bir kuni* butun No'g'ayqo'rg'on dahasi choyxonaga yig'ilib maylis qildi (O'H, Xayollarga bo'laman tutqin, 47);

- **All day – kuni bo'yi, ertalabdan kechgacha:** "Why, Bill. I've been looking for him *all day*." (OH, The Princes and the Puma, 43); *Ertalabdan kechgacha* ichkilikbozlik qilishib, o'zlarining baxtiqaro onalarini kaltaklash bilan shug'ullanishadi. (EH,142);

- **The next day – ertasi kuni:** *The next day* he waited, impatient, in his rooms for the word. (OH, Confessions of a Humorist, 80);

- **Last night – kecha kechqurun:** I was tight last night (EH, 78); *Ertasiga kechqurun* Qonqus yoqasida – Alimardonning eng baxtiyor, eng pokiza damlari – bolalik yillari kechgan o'sha anhor yoqasida jimgina mudrab yotgan go'ristonda yana bir qabr mungli do'ppaydi. (O'H, Cho'l havosi,275);

- **The same day – o'sha kunioq:** *The same* night his employer's safe was robbed. (OH, Blind man's holiday, 21); *O'sha kunioq* singlimdan uyingizga xat berib yuborgandim. Akam eshik oldida ko'rib qolib, xatni tortib olibdi... (O'H, Xayollarga bo'laman tutqin, 55);

- **Every morning/every evening – har ertalab/har kechqurun:** It is worth a paragraph to say that this remarkable scene can be witnessed *every evening* in numerous cafes in the City of New York. (OH, A cosmopolite in a café,8);

Har sahar turarman va yakkash

O'zimdanda ohista so'rarman:

"Bilmadim, bu nening talqini,

Bog'larda erta kuz salqini..." (O'H, Uzun kechalar, 65)

- **Each year – har yili:** The good ones came each year (EH, 124); Onasi uni *har yili* bolalar oromgohiga yuborardi. (O'H, Qalbingga quloq sol, 386);

Temporallikni ifodalashda ergashgan qo'shma gaplarning roli katta. S.Ya. Abdullayevaning "Payt ergash gapli qo'shma gaplar sintaksisi" mavzusidagi nomzodlik tadqiqotida ta'kidlanishicha, aksariyat hollarda payt ergash gapli qo'shma gaplarda u yoki bu zamon shakllarining, u yoki bu boshqa payt bog'lovchilarining qo'llanishi qo'shma gapda qo'llanilgan

fe'ning aksional (chegaralangan/chegaralanmagan) ma'nolariga va ular yordamida ifodalangan aspektual vaziyatlarga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Aytish joizki, bunday holda payt ergash gapning kesimi ifodalagan ish-harakat semantikasini bosh gap kesimi ifodalagan semantika bilan qiyoslaganda, ergash gap kesimining ish-harakati bosh gap kesimi ish-harakatidan oldin, keyin yoki bir paytda bajarilishiga qarab tahlil qilish mumkin. Ammo, ingliz tili payt ergash gapli qo'shma gaplar tarkibida temporallikni ifodalovchi bog'lovchilarning roli beqiyos.

Payt ergash gaplarning bosh gap bilan bog'lanishida *while*, *after*, *as*, *what time* kabilar ham qo'llaniladi:

- *While* Cogan was describing to me the topography along the Siberian Railway the orchestra glided into a medley. (OH, *A cosmopolite in a café*,8); Uylanayotganimda ko'zim qayoqda edi! (O'H, *Bahor qaytmaydi*, 201);

- *After* we got back to the hotel and Klein had gone, Silver jumps at me and waves his hands. (OH, *Blind man`s holiday*,16); ...Aqlimni taniganimdan keyin bilsam, men shirin, beg'ubor tush ko'rayotgan ekanman-u, To'lash bir og'iz gapi bilan ustimdan muzday sovuq suv quyib, uyg'otib yuborgan ekan. (O'H, *Hurkitilgan qush*, 33);

- *As* we started along the road he turned and walked back toward the inn (EH,122); Hakim sassiq urushdan kelgach, polizda brigadir bo'lib ishlardi.(O'H, *Hurkitilgan qush*, 29);

- *I don't know what time* I got to bed (EH,138); Bora-bora Charosning qaysi kuni, soat nechada darsi tugashini bilib oldi. (O'H, *Qalbingga quloq sol*, 423).

Xulosa

Temporallikni ifodalovchi sintaktik birliklar sodda gaplar tarkibida ishtirok etganda, aynan o'sha gapning kesimi ifodalagan ish-harakatning bajarilish payti anglashiladi, ya'ni so'zlovchi o'zining suhbatdoshiga ish-harakatning bajarilganligi, bajarilayotganini, bajarilish paytini aniq ma'lum qiladi. Demak, sodda gap qurilmasida temporallik elementlarining ifodalanishi adverbial birliklar: *yet-hali*, *never-hech qachon*, *now-hozir*, *still-hamon*, *ever-bir paytlar*, *once-bir vaqtlar*, *just-bir paytlari*, *already-allaqachon*, *always-har doim*, *hamisha*, *then-keyin*, *shu payt*, *o'shanda*, *bu paytda*, *sometimes-ba'zan*, *at once-darrov*, *during-bu paytda*, *mobaynida*, *soon now-ko'pi ketib ozi qolmoq* kabilar yordamida ifodalasa, temporallikni ifodalovchi predlogli birikmalar *after+ot-otdan keyin* *ot+before-bundan+son+oldin*, *before+ot-ot+dan oldin*, *at+ ot-ot+sifotdosh+da*, *ot+son+da*, *for+ son+ot- son+ ot+davomida*, *in va by* predloglari esa vaqtni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar bilan birikib kelishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, *yesterday*, *tomorrow*, *tonight*, *day* hafta kunlarini ifodalovchi leksik birliklar *one*, *all*, *next*, *last*, *same*, *each* kabi bog'lovchilar yordamida birikib, bosh gapdagi ish-harakat bilan payt ergash gapdagi ish-harakatni taqqoslab, kesimlar ifodalagan ish-harakatning bajarilishiga aniqlik kiritadi.

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К ВОПРОСУ О РЕФЕРЕНЦИИ ЭКСПРЕССИВНЫХ И ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФРАЗЕОСЕМ

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Аннотация: Рассматривается характер значения фразеологических единиц, обуславливающий конкретность экспрессивных и эмоциональных фразеосем во фразеологизмах с частично переосмысленными компонентами. Кроме того, в статье анализируются примеры, которые показывают экспрессивность и эмоциональность фразеосем в предложениях. Эмоциональные выражения необходимы для подкрепления сообщений, передачи реальности и создания доверия, поэтому выражение эмоций важно в общении на научной основе. Виды экспрессивных и эмоциональных фразеосем раскрыты с помощью примеров которые взяты из англоязычной художественной литературы.

Ключевые слова: фразеосема, семантика, мотивированность, немотивированность, фразеологическая единица, денотат, экспрессия.

TO THE QUESTION OF THE REFERENCE OF EXPRESSIVE AND EMOTIONAL PHRASEOSEMES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the nature of the meaning of phraseological units is considered, which determines the specificity of expressive and emotional phraseosemes in phraseological units with partially rethought components. In addition, the article analyzes examples that show the expressiveness and emotionality of phraseosemes in sentences. Emotional expressions are necessary to reinforce messages, convey reality and create trust, therefore the expression of emotions is important in communication on a scientific basis. Types of expressive and emotional phraseoses are revealed using examples taken from English fictions.

Keywords: phraseoseme, semantics, motivation, lack of motivation, phraseological unit, denotation, expression.

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